

AFRICANISATION AND THE TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE TEACHING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR CURRICULUM REFORMATION

Seabata Ambrose Mohatle¹, Bridgett Mangwegape

¹Mr., Central University of Technology, South Africa, smohatle@cut.ac.za;

²Dr. Central University of Technology, South Africa, bmangwegape@cut.ac.za

Abstract

It has long been acknowledged that there is a disagreement about the benefits of imparting traditional knowledge. There has not been much discussion on how TK can be taught in theory and practice to fit any field of science. As it respects diversity and acknowledges the challenge of hegemony of Western-cantered forms of universal knowledge, TK can empower communities to participate in their educational development. However, the debate on curriculum transformation and Africanization has made it critical for scholars and students alike to seriously consider TK as a catalyst in education. This paper is a review of the literature with a particular emphasis on how TK instruction can change African educational system, which is frequently out of touch with local reality. The conclusion of the paper highlights the necessity for African universities and the education sector to serve as a means of enhancing the socioeconomic and political conditions of the country's citizens. The conclusion of the paper highlights the necessity for African universities and the education sector to serve as a means of enhancing the socioeconomic and political conditions of the country's citizens.

Keywords: traditional knowledge (TK), Africanisation, curriculum transformation

1. INTRODUCTION

On a national and worldwide scale, traditional knowledge (TK) is an area of study that is expanding rapidly. A lively discussion about Africanization and curriculum reform has also taken place at the same time. Several South African universities currently offer comprehensive TK coursework at the undergraduate and graduate levels. These courses are occasionally available as electives in different programs. TK courses are being used by students from all scientific inquiry domains to comprehend the context of their own knowledge fields, particularly those that define their African background. Students and scholars are calling for a departure from European-cantered knowledge systems in keeping with the call for the transformation of the Africanization of knowledge. The majority of African scholars and students have begun to actively challenge the notion of TK. This remains the case even though there has been a continuous discussion about it in both historical and contemporary educational literature.

TK does not have a single, widely accepted definition. Context heavily influences how TK is defined, and most of the time, scholars that are Eurocentric try to conceptualize IK as a foreign cognitive system. Noyoo ((2007) defines the traditional knowledge system (TKS) as the intricate collection of knowledge, abilities, and technologies that have been created and preserved in relation to local demographic and indigenous

community conditions in a certain geographic location. TKS is the understanding that members of a particular community have acquired throughout time and are still acquiring.

This is in contrast to the stereotypical setting, where traditional knowledge (TK) and indigenous knowledge (IK) are synonymous terms that denote a static, ancient body of knowledge that has been passed down through the generations. In the African setting, IK is not viewed in this way. Only the knowledge, customs, and methods employed by indigenous peoples are the focus of the stereotypical approach, which also records their local names and catalogues their purported purposes. This cognitive process consequently introduces bias into the teaching of IK. African scholarship has just begun delving deeply into research that demonstrates this prejudice. In addition to pursuing knowledge, a growing number of academics are working to make sure African views are recognized. It is now crucial to realize that African problems must be seen in the perspective of African resolutions.

In keeping with what was said above, Africanization is now recognized as a revitalized emphasis on Africa and involves restoring what has been taken from the continent. According to the previous explanation, it is a process of bringing back the original "living or people's knowledge." there is no denying colonialism's detrimental effects on TK. Reviving the positive aspects of African culture is known as "Africanization." The knowledge that before colonialism, Africa and its people lived in modern peace and harmony calls for further research into the conditions that led to this. Colonialism has a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach. All facets of life were impacted, but the most concerning development was the widespread voluntary and, frequently, coerced abandonment of Africans' ingrained knowledge systems due to the perception that they were primitive, archaic, and unholy. IK was demonized. According to Ramose, the indigenous conquered peoples lacked an epistemology and a philosophy that would have been valuable to include in any curriculum. This was the opinion of the colonial conqueror and his successor in title.

African values have been marginalized for many years by an educational system that exclusively promotes Western ideals. The intention of the colonizers was to rid the black people of anything African as early as the 18th century. The "Bantu education" system in South Africa served as a tool to limit the intellectual growth of Black African students by falsifying school curriculum and maintaining authority over both teachers' and students' knowledge. Therefore, Africanization is a feasible idea to alter this situation. In addition to rejecting subservience to foreign masters and defending African rights and interests, there is a clarion call for the revival of what was honorable and valued in African culture. Trauma throughout generations has resulted from colonization. Despite this, African knowledge systems have a rich history because they have influenced and defined African culture for many generations. TK refused to pass away and disappear off the face of the universe because of the "way of life." TK is being reevaluated piecemeal and is seen as a great source of sustainable development initiatives. Any knowledge field can be contextualized to the environment in which it is delivered by African knowledge systems. It offers a method that would allow pupils to actively participate in learning about their surroundings. As a result, despite the colonial master's best efforts, it proved impossible to eradicate entirely off the face of the planet. Many African nations have struggled to achieve economic and social freedom since gaining their independence. There is only a certain amount of political independence in most situations. Thus, it is imperative that Africans take on the colonial knowledge system in order to achieve full freedom. It can be seen as a demand to modify curriculum and syllabi in order to ensure that teaching and learning are tailored to African contexts and realities when it is connected to higher education. Consequently, TK instruction can be a useful instrument in the curriculum's decolonization and Africanization. Africans' realization of the value of their continental heritage would be a prerequisite for any serious transformation of education throughout the continent.

The idea of "Africanization" is currently given the decontextualized status of curriculum and the stereotypical character of knowledge creation and dissemination in South African higher education and Africa at large. The paper addresses the significance of incorporating TK into the classroom while drawing attention to the ongoing discussion about the Africanization of the curriculum. We have an advantage when it comes to creating pertinent African curriculum since we employ insider viewpoints on knowledge development. Seepe (2004), asserts that a comprehensive reorganization of African education that integrates knowledge to address the continent's problems would be difficult to accomplish without giving IK due consideration. If given careful thought, TK has the potential to be the real catalyst for modern teaching.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

the current south African constitutional and language policy frameworks put at the forefront the growth of previously discriminated indigenous African languages. It further recommends both positive and practical

initiatives to be employed by all government parastatals and private sector for the promotion of indigenous African languages (Beukes 2008). The Department of basic Education is committed to the implementation of multilingualism agenda, the development of all official languages and the equal treatment of all languages used in the country, including south African sign languages and other languages referred to in the constitution (Department of Education, 1997). It is for this reason therefore that this paper is theoretically grounded on the concept of language-as-a-resource position which stresses the importance of multilingualism, as a facilitator of access to learning and as a door to economic opportunities (Gumbi & Ndimande-Hlongwa, 2015:157).

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Current curriculum that are improper and irrelevant contribute to the modern discourse that characterizes TK as less scholarly and outdated. The goal of Africanizing higher education lends support to the need for TK and its teachings to be acknowledged. These two elements might be seen as the subject matter's and the teaching strategies' adaptation to the physical and cultural reality of the African context.

3.1 What constitutes traditional knowledge?

A universally accepted definition of TK is hard to find. The definition given here is one that is supported by the context of this paper. TK is described as the knowledge systems developed by a community as opposed to the scientific knowledge that is generally referred to as 'modern' knowledge. Indigenous knowledge is the basis for local-level decision-making in many rural communities. TK constitutes the knowledge that people in a given community have developed over time and continue to develop. It has value not only for the culture in which it evolves, but also for scientists and planners striving to improve conditions in rural localities. Accordingly, TK is defined as a combination of knowledge systems consisting of technology, social, economic and philosophical learning. Indigenous communities themselves believe that their IK is their constantly refined wisdom that has been passed on from their ancestors and the elders in their communities with a capability to survive for many centuries in the unique locations they identify as their homelands. This knowledge is naturally passed down from one generation to another. In addition to this definition, (Ellen & Harris 2000), conclude that TK is localised to a particular place and is generated by people living in those places. It is manifested through trial and error and deliberate experiment. TK is alive to evolution that stands the test of time. In its full realisation, IK is holistic, integrative, situated within the broader cultural traditions, and is empirical rather than hypothetical. This is also to say TK is a 'living science' or a peoples' science, it is not static but changes with the times. Linking the above explanation to Africanisation means TK is compatible with African knowledge systems that are now a big reference point of research in Southern Africa and beyond.

3.2 What is meant by "Africanization"?

Africanization is the process of integrating African culture into formal education through educational reform. Africanization, according to Makgoba (1996), is an inclusive process that emphasizes the value of promoting African cultures and identities within the global community. He goes on to say that for Africans, it's a way of life and a process of learning. It incorporates, adapts, and integrates different cultures into African visions without being exclusive in order to offer the vitality, evolution, and adaptability that are so necessary in today's globalized society.

Because they can integrate knowledge systems from outside of Africa, African knowledge systems are therefore not wholly indigenous. It implies that IK need not be abandoned in favor of westernization because the two may coexist when doing so benefits Africans. Paradoxically, the knowledge systems of other continents have also been impacted by African knowledge systems. Several Western pharmaceutical corporations have made a significant push in recent decades to fund research and development initiatives aimed at determining the potential medical benefits of indigenous people' traditional medicines.

Le Grange (2004) concurs with the notion that Western and African knowledge systems may coexist. Consequently, Africanization will indicate that the ingrained Western knowledge systems currently in use in Africa are not being replaced. A sense of security must be ingrained; only then can Africa learn from the West without worrying that the African character would be destroyed by changes. This essay makes the case that in order for Western knowledge systems to be useful and effective in African cultures, they must be modified to fit the African environment. Furthermore, there is a lot that African knowledge systems can teach Western knowledge systems.

According to Mutwa (1997), people in Western civilization live in a world of separatism where objects that should be viewed as a part of a larger whole are divided. Conversely, as demonstrated by African knowledge systems, education must represent the unity of disparate aspects of life. The indigenization of African knowledge systems would be a component of Africanization. This turn becomes an exercise in identifying or interpreting African culture and identity. By defining it as an African experience that serves as a source for the creation of knowledge, Ramose broadens this idea. (Higgs, 2003) refers to the idea of "ubuntu" and the characteristics of humanity, loyalty, and humanistic aspirations that it represents.

Many people interpret ubuntu as communalism and humanism.²⁸ This explains why African identity is intrinsic to a living system of knowledge. Because of this, (Mbingi, 2000) argues that the word "ubuntu" literally translates to "I am because you are"—a person can only exist because of other people. True humanity is derived from relationships between members of a community. This "ubuntu" quality—which is the main source of strength for the African people—became one of the weak points when imperialism took advantage of it by accepting other people and their ideas with ease.

Almsgiving, sympathy, caring, sensitivity to the needs of others, respect, regard, patience, and kindness are all characteristics of humanism, according to Prinsloo (1997). This humanistic feature is valued more highly than the drive to profit from new discoveries and technologies, particularly in the pharmaceutical sector.

. In contrast to a Western doctor, whose mandate and the constraints of running a business will typically influence him to seek compensation for the services rendered, an African traditional healer is more likely to treat the illness or disease of a fellow villager for free and even share the knowledge of the traditional medicine. According to Waghid (2004), IK with African influences has the power to encourage people to be just, courageous, and truthful.

In relating this to the definition of Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) as given by some of its ideas, Parker (2003), discusses Africanized scholarship and how the idea of "critical activism" pertaining to justice and human rights should be included. This is another "ubuntu" characteristic. Every student's educational journey must include this in order to provide them with the skills necessary to contribute positively to society. A system of education is appropriate if it produces graduates who are ready to give back to their home communities. Furthermore, the maximization of social welfare is the ultimate goal of IP legislation, according to the utilitarian approach.

Therefore, it's important to find a balance between promoting innovation and invention and making sure that social welfare doesn't go neglected. (Louw, 2020) contend that parliamentarians and the Western legal system, which is common in African nations, must defend IK. At that point, it is clear that Africanization is having the desired effect. According to (Louw), Africanization is a means of recognizing and embracing "otherness," as well as a means of transcending particular identities and looking for commonalities.

IK has the chance to propose an inclusive method of teaching. African leaders like Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana and Julius Nyerere of Tanzania were founded on these ideals. It is important that they recognize the village or community as an extension of their family, extending beyond the tribe. The African continent became free of colonialism as a result of the founding fathers of African emancipation's outstanding accomplishments from their village-based worldview.

Communitarianism results from people viewing themselves as part of a community rather than as independent individuals. Understanding the characteristics of Africanization of IP and how it should be taught is essential to persuading practitioners and students alike of the significance of this vital topic. Nkrumah and Nyerere accepted the notion of wide inclusion as a virtue. This was not the original idea; rather, the acceptance of this characteristic across a large portion of Africa suggests that Africans were exemplars of this virtue. Students studying Intellectual Property (IP) in this context will be better equipped to clarify to community stakeholders the implications of IP protection for their intellectual property (IK). The voices of the community's stakeholders must be heard and be considered as valuable contributions to the body of science.

There is a desire to design curricula that are inclusive in the topic above. Numerous academics have also made the case for IK needing to have the same level of protection as IP in the spirit of inclusion. This is especially crucial when it comes to sui generis arrangements that defend certain individual nations. Nkoane provides an explanation of an educational system that is Africanized and keeps Africans aware of the social structure and cultural development guidelines. It is described as "education within an African context" by Higgs and van Wyk (2007) and it focuses on the fundamental beliefs and values that make up education

within an African environment, as well as how Africans acquire and produce knowledge. Furthermore, encouraging awareness of African consciousness while enabling an educational framework that would produce information that is useful, efficient, and empowering. Collaboration and cooperation between universities and communities may soon become strained if African consciousness is overlooked in our educational system. This is especially true if the academic knowledge produced looks disconnected from or irrelevant to the realities of peoples' everyday lives. On the ecological links found in nature, the African IK is founded. When individuals perceive that their customs and values are not valued, they may become less inclined to interact with outside specialists. It's possible that the knowledge we acquire won't be useful in addressing problems in the real world. Contextual considerations make knowledge useless. Both the creation of knowledge and the formulation of educational objectives must take Africans' immediate environments into consideration. Most of the students at the North- West University IKS Centre in South Africa do their research in their home areas. According to my experience grading the work produced by this exercise, the community's involvement in the study greatly enhances its value. The goal of Africanizing the curricula is to enable students to employ contextualized theories in order to perform work that is best practiced. The curriculum's decolonization gives pupils the ability to create their own understanding of the African setting and to impart knowledge in a way that is sensitive to cultural differences. This means that there must be a major focus on questioning the status quo and the applicability of Western theories and current knowledge systems in the African setting.

3.3 Opportunities of integrating traditional knowledge within basic education sector

Improving TK and the quality of education in South Africa will greatly benefit from the incorporation of TK into CT and learning. According to Osborn (2010), without TK, it is impossible to reproduce knowledge and disseminate local content and knowledge in CT. It is a commonly held belief that multilingualism must be supported by the deployment of programs that facilitate learning and knowledge production in literacy and in classes using a primary language (Cummins 2000). It is further asserted that learning through the use of indigenous African language preserves these languages and improves the quality of education and if they are integrated into CT especially if introduced in the early years of childhood (Kamwangamalu 2000). Disappointingly so, the use of TK as alternative tools for learning and teaching is still continuously restricted to disadvantaged schools in the townships and rural areas (Lafon 2008). Kamwangamalu (2000), posits that the use of home languages for teaching and learning enhances lessons and making them more interesting.

3.4 Challenges of integrating traditional knowledge into information

In practice however, the adoption and integration of African languages into CT is a challenging and complex process for schools, particularly where there are limited resources in ICT to support teaching and learning. Infrastructural challenges and absence of TK in education in particular have compromised the nation- wide application of CT in education initiatives (ED, 2015). Other problems that seem to affect the integration of TK and communication technology (CT) in basic Education languages into ICT must be viewed within the context of the various related factors of localization ecology that affect the process of ICT localization namely society, language, economics, technology, education and politics. The ability to create and share local content such as administrative, tourist, or instructional content—on the Internet is diminished when ICTs are not offered in a particular local language. Consequently, there is a diminished likelihood that the culture represented by this language will be disseminated and made available to speakers, scholars, and linguists who wish to study it (Osborn 2010).

4. CONCLUSION

The South African government needs to make every effort to stop the digital marginalization of indigenous African languages if it is sincere about participating in the knowledge economy. This is primarily due to the global education revolution that is now occurring. This change is being propelled not only by the evolving nature of employment but also by the people's compact, which requires the government to provide equal possibilities for education. Incorporating Traditional Knowledge (TK) into Communication Technology (CT) is crucial for the preservation of native African languages as well as improving learning within the foundational education system.

The main advantages of adding these languages as extra instruments to help address the school system's current problems. Since most South African teachers come from underprivileged schools, they require pedagogical expertise in order to translate CT curriculum. As a result, teacher CT training is essential and will be crucial to their ability to grow and make use of CT-specific resources. The emphasis must be on the

applicable, real-world experiences of educators and students using the resources at their disposal in the context of their subject areas of study, all the while using traditional knowledge.

REFERENCE LIST

- Cummings, C. (2000). *Winning Strategies for Classroom Management: ASCD*. ASCD.
- Beukes, A. M. (2008). Language policy implementation in South Africa: How Kempton Park's great expectations are dashed in Tshwane. *Stellenbosch papers in Linguistics*, 38, 1-26. Department of Education. (2015). KwaZulu-Natal circular no. 10. DoE.
- Department of Education. (1997). *Language in Education Policy*. Pretoria: DoE. Ellen & Harris 2000),
- Ellen RF & Harris H, 'H. (2000) (Introduction' in R Ellen, P Parkes, and A. Bicker (Eds.), *Indigenous Environmental Knowledge and its Transformations: Critical anthropological perspectives* (Amsterdam: Harwood,), 33.
- Fafunwa, B. (1990). Using national languages in education: A challenge to African educators. *African thoughts on the prospects of education for all*, 97-110.)
- Higgs P. (2003). 'African philosophy and the transformation of educational discourse in South Africa' *African Journal of Education*
- Higgs P & Van Wyk B (2007) 'Lifelong Learning Revisited: An African Educational Discourse' 11, *Education Change*
- Kamwangamalu. N. M. (2000). A new language policy, old language practices: Status planning for African languages in a multilingual South Africa. *South African journal of African languages*, 20(1), 50-60.
- Lafon, M. (2008). Asikhulume! African Language for All. A Powerful strategy for spearheading transformation and Improvement of the south African Education system. In Lafon, M & V Webb (eds): *the standardisation of African Languages in south Africa: Language Political realities*. Johannesburg, South Africa: Institut
- Francaisd•Afrique du & Le Grange L. (2004) 'Western science and indigenous knowledge: competing perspectives or complementary frameworks?' *South African Journal of Higher Education*
- Louw W. ((2010). Africanisation: a rich environment for active learning on a global platform' *Progression*.
- Makgoba, M. (1996) 'The Makgoba affair': A reflection on transformation (Florida: Vivlia),
- Makgoba, M., & Seepe, S. (2004). Knowledge and identity: An African vision of higher education transformation. *Towards an African identity of higher education*, 13-58.
- Mbingi L. (2000) 'In search of the African business renaissance: an African culture perspective Randburg: Knowledge Resources
- Mutwa C.V. (1997). 'Isilwane the animal' Cape Town
- Noyoo N. (2007) 'Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Their Relevance for Sustainable Development' A Case of Southern Africa
- Osborn. D.Z (2010). *African Languages in a Digital Age: challenges and Opportunities for Indigenous Language computing*. cape town: Hsrc Press. [36] Osborn DZ. 2006. *African Languages*
- Parker B (2003) 'Back on the Chain Gang: Some Difficulties in Developing a (South) African Philosophy of Education' 30 *Journal of Education*
- Prinsloo E.D. (1997). 'Ubuntu culture and participatory management' in PH Cotzee & APJ Roux (eds) *The African Philosophy reader* (London: Routledge, 1997) Ramose MB 'In search of an
- Seepe S 'Editorial notes' (2004) 18 South African Journal of Higher Education.
- (Waghid Y. (2004). African philosophy of education: Implications for teaching and learning' 18 *South African Journal of Higher Education*